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Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London

London Academic Press, [etc.] 1833-1965

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pt.9-11 (1841-1843):

<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/96442>

Article/Chapter Title: Charlesworth_1841

Page(s): Page 55, Page 56, Page 57, Page 58, Page 59, Page 60,
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July 13, 1841.

Professor Owen, Vice-President, in the Chair.

The following letter, addressed to Mr. Waterhouse, from James Brooke, Esq., was read:—

“ Singapore, 25th March, 1841.

“ My dear Sir,—I am happy to announce the departure of five live Orang Utans by the ship *Martin Luther*, Captain Swan, and I trust they will reach you alive. In case they die, I have directed Captain Swan to put them into spirit, that you may still have an opportunity of seeing them. The whole of the five are from Borneo: one large female adult from Sambas; two, with slight cheek callosities, from Pontiana; a small male, without any sign of callosities, from Pontiana likewise; and the smallest of all, a very young male with callosities, from Sadung. I will shortly forward a fine collection of skulls and skeletons from the north-west coast of Borneo, either shot by myself or brought by the natives, and I beg you will do me the favour to present the live Orangs and this collection to the Zoological Society. I have made many inquiries and gained some information regarding these animals, and I can, beyond a doubt, prove the existence of two, if not three distinct species in Borneo.

“ First, I will re-state the native account; secondly, give you my own observations; and thirdly, enter into a brief detail of the specimens hereafter to be forwarded.

“ 1st. The natives of the north-west coast of Borneo are all positive as to the existence of two distinct species, which I formerly gave you by the names of the *Mias Pappan* and *Mias Rambi*; but I have since received information from a few natives of intelligence that there are three sorts, and what is vulgarly called the *Mias Rambi* is in reality the *Mias Kassar*, the *Rambi* being a distinct and third species. The *Mias Pappan* is the *Simia Wurmbii* of Mr. Owen, having callosities on the sides of the face: the natives treat with derision the idea of the *Mias Kassar* or *Simia Morio* being the female of the *Mias Pappan* or *Simia Wurmbii*, and I consider the fact can be established so clearly that I will not trouble you with their statements: both Malays and Dyaks are positive that the female of the *Mias Pappan* has cheek-callosities, the same as the male; and if on inquiry it prove to be so, the existence of three distinct species in Borneo will be established. The existence of the *Mias Rambi* is vouched by a few natives only, but they were men of intelligence and well acquainted with the animals in the wild state. They represent the *Mias Rambi* to be as tall as the *Pappan*, or even taller, but not so stout, with longer hair, a smaller face, and no callosities either on the male or female, and they always insisted that it was not the female of the *Pappan*.

“ The *Mias Kassar* or *Simia Morio* is the same colour as the *Mias*
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Pappan, but altogether smaller, and devoid of callosities either on the male or female adults.

“By the native statements, therefore, we find three distinct species, viz. the *Mias Pappan* or *Simia Wurmbii*, the *Mias Kassar* or *Simia Morio*, and the *Mias Rambii*, which is either the *Simia Abelii* or a fourth species. The existence of the Sumatran Orang in Borneo is by no means impossible, and I have already compared so many of the native statements that I place more confidence in them than I did formerly, more especially as their account is in a great measure borne out by the skulls in my possession. I had an opportunity of seeing the *Mias Pappan* and the *Mias Kassar* in their native woods, and killing one of the former and several of the latter species. The distribution of these animals is worthy of notice, as they are found both at Pontiana and Sambas in considerable numbers, and at Sadung on the north-west coast, but are unknown in the intermediate country which includes the rivers of Sarawak and Samarahan. I confess myself at a loss to account for their absence on the Sarawak and Samarahan rivers, which abound with fruit, and have forests similar and contiguous to the Sadung Linga and other rivers. The distance from Samarahan to Sadung does not exceed twenty-five miles, and though pretty abundant on the latter, they are unknown on the former river. From Sadung, proceeding to the northward and eastward, they are found for about 100 miles, but beyond that distance do not inhabit the forests. The *Mias Pappan* and *Mias Kassar* inhabit the same woods, but I never met them on the same day; both species, according to the natives, are equally common, but from my own experience the *Mias Kassar* is the most plentiful. The *Mias Rambii* is represented as unfrequent and rarely to be met with. The *Pappan* is justly named *Satyrus* from the ugly face and disgusting callosities. The adult male I killed was seated lazily on a tree, and when approached only took the trouble to interpose the trunk between us, peeping at me and dodging as I dodged. I hit him on the wrist and he was afterwards despatched. I send you his proportions, enormous relative to his height, and until I came to actual measurement my impression was that he was nearly six feet in stature. The following is an extract from my journal relating to him, noted down directly after he was killed.

“Great was our triumph as we gazed on the huge animal dead at our feet, and proud were we of having shot the first Orang we had seen, and shot him in his native woods, in a Borneo forest, hitherto untrodden by European feet. The animal was adult, having four incisors, two canines and ten molars in each jaw, but by his general appearance he was not old. We were struck by the length of his arms, the enormous neck, and the expanse of face, which altogether gave the impression of great height, whereas it was only great power. The hair was long, reddish and thin; the face remarkably broad and fleshy, and on each side, in the place of a man's whiskers, were the callosities or rather fleshy protuberances, which I was so desirous to see, and which were nearly two inches in thickness. The ears were small and well-shaped, the nose quite flat, mouth prominent,

lips thick, teeth large and discoloured, eyes small and roundish, face and hands black, the latter being very powerful.

“ ‘ The following are the dimensions :—

	Ft.	In.
Height from head to heel	4	1
Length of foot	1	0
Ditto hand	0	10 $\frac{1}{2}$
Length of arm from shoulder-blade to finger end..	3	5 $\frac{3}{4}$
Shoulder-blade to elbow	1	6
Elbow to wrist	1	1 $\frac{1}{2}$
Hip to heel	1	9
Head to <i>Os coccygis</i>	2	5 $\frac{1}{2}$
Across the shoulders	1	5 $\frac{1}{2}$
Circumference of neck	2	4
Ditto below the ribs	3	3 $\frac{1}{4}$
Ditto under the arms	3	0
From forehead to chin	0	9 $\frac{3}{4}$
Across the face, below the eyes, including callosities	1	1
From ear to ear across the top of head	0	9 $\frac{1}{2}$
From ear to ear behind the head	0	9 $\frac{3}{4}$

“ ‘ The natives asserted the animal to be a small one, but I am sceptical of their ever attaining the growth of a tall man, though I bear in mind that full-grown animals will probably differ as much in height as man.’

“ Some days after this, and about thirty miles distant, I was fortunate enough to kill two adult females (one with her young), and a male nearly adult, all the *Mias Kassar*. The young male was not measured, owing to my having waded up to my neck in pursuit of him, and thereby destroyed my paper and lost my measure; but he certainly did not exceed three feet, whilst the two females were about 3ft. 1in. and 3ft. 2in. in height. The male was just cutting his two posterior molars: the colour of all resembled that of the *Mias Pappan*, but the difference between the two animals was apparent even to our seamen. The *Kassar* has no callosities either on the male or female, whereas the young *Pappans* despatched by the Martin Luther (one of them *not a year old*, with two first molars) show them prominently. The great difference between the *Kassar* and the *Pappan* in size would prove at once the distinction of the two species, the *Kassar* being a small slight animal, by no means formidable in his appearance, with hands and feet *proportioned* to the body, and they do not approach the gigantic extremities of the *Pappan* either in size or power; and, in short, a moderately powerful man would readily overpower one, when he would not stand the shadow of a chance with the *Pappan*. Besides these decisive differences, may be mentioned the appearance of the face, which in the *Mias Kassar* is more prominent in the lower part, and the eyes exteriorly larger, in proportion to the size of the animal, than in the *Pappan*. The colour of the skin in the adult *Pappans* is black, whilst the *Kassar*, in his face and hands, has the dirty colour common to the young of both

species. If further evidence was wanted, the skulls will fully prove the distinction of species, for the skulls of two adult animals compared will show a difference *in size alone* which must preclude all supposition of their being one species. Mr. Owen's remarks are, however, so conclusive, that I need not dwell on this point; and with a suite of skulls, male and female, from the adult to the infant, of the *Mias Kassar*, which I shall have the pleasure to forward, there can remain, I should think, little further room for discussion. I may mention, however, that two young animals I had in my possession alive, one a *Kassar*, the other a *Pappan*, fully bore out these remarks by their proportionate size. The *Pappan*, with two molars, showed the callosities distinctly, and was as tall and far stouter than the *Kassar* with three molars, whilst the *Kassar* had no vestige of the callosities. Their mode of progression likewise was different, as the *Kassar* doubled his fists and dragged his hind quarters after him, whilst the *Pappan* supported himself on the open hands sideways placed on the ground, and moved one leg before the other in the erect sitting attitude; but this was only observed in the two young ones, and cannot be considered as certainly applicable to all.

“ On the habits of the Orangs, as far as I have been able to observe them, I may remark, that they are as dull and as slothful as can well be conceived, and on no occasion when pursuing them did they move so fast as to preclude my keeping pace with them easily through a moderately clear forest; and even when obstructions below (such as wading up to the neck) allowed them to get away some distance, they were sure to stop and allow us to come up. I never observed the slightest attempt at defence, and the wood, which sometimes rattled about our ears, was broken by their weight, and not thrown, as some persons represent. If pushed to extremity, however, the *Pappan* could not be otherwise than formidable; and one unfortunate man, who with a party was trying to catch a large one alive, lost two of his fingers, besides being severely bitten on the face, whilst the animal finally beat off his pursuers and escaped. When they wish to catch an adult they cut down a circle of trees round the one on which he is seated, and then fell that also, and close before he can recover himself, and endeavour to bind him.

“ In a small work entitled ‘The Menageries,’ published in 1838, there is a good account of the Bornean Orang, with a brief extract from Mr. Owen's valuable paper on the *Simia Morio*; but, after dwelling on the lazy and apathetic disposition of the animal, it states in the same page that they can make their way amid the branches of the trees with *surprising agility*, whereas they are the slowest and least active of all the monkey tribe, and their motions are surprisingly awkward and uncouth. The natives on the north-west coast entertain no dread, and always represent the Orangs as harmless and inoffensive animals; and from what I saw, they would never attack a man unless brought to the ground. The rude *hut* which they are stated to build in the trees would be more properly called a seat or nest, for it has no roof or cover of any sort. The facility with which they form this seat is curious, and I

had an opportunity of seeing a wounded female weave the branches together, and seat herself within a minute; she afterwards received our fire without moving, and expired in her lofty abode, whence it cost us much trouble to dislodge her. I have seen some individuals with nails on the posterior thumbs, but generally speaking they are devoid of them: of the five animals sent home, two have the nails and three are devoid of them; one has the nail well-formed, and in the other it is merely rudimentary. The length of my letter precludes my dwelling on many particulars, which, as I have not seen the recent publications on the subject, might be mere repetitions, and I will only mention, as briefly as I can, the skulls of these animals in my possession. From my late sad experience I am induced to this, that some brief record may be preserved from shipwreck. These skulls may be divided into three distinct sorts. The first presents two ridges, one rising from each frontal bone, which joining on the top of the head, form an elevated crest, which runs backward to the cerebral portion of the skull.

“The second variety is the *Simia Morio*, and nothing need be added to Mr. Owen’s account, save that it presents no ridge whatever beyond the frontal part of the head. No. 9 in the collection is the skull of an adult male: No. 2 the male, nearly adult, killed by myself: Nos. 11 and 3 adult females, killed by myself: No. 12 a young male, with three molars, killed by myself: No. 21 a young male, died aboard, with three molars: No. 19, young male, died aboard, with two molars. There are many other skulls of the *Simia Morio* which exactly coincide with this suite, and this suite so remarkably coincides through the different stages of age, one with another, that no doubt can exist of the *Simia Morio* being a distinct species. The different character of the skull, its small size and small teeth, put the matter beyond doubt, and completely establish Mr. Owen’s acute and triumphant argument, drawn from a single specimen.

“The third distinction of the skulls is, that the ridges rising from the frontal bones do not meet, but converge towards the top of the head, and again diverge towards the posterior portion of the skull. These ridges are less elevated than in the first-mentioned skulls, but the size of the adult skulls is equal, and both present specimens of aged animals. For a long time I was inclined to think the skulls with the double ridge were the females of the animals with the single and more prominent ridge, but No. 1 (already described as killed by myself) will show that the double ridge belongs to an adult, and not young male animal, and that it belongs to the *Simia Wurmbii* with the huge callosities. The distinction therefore cannot be a distinction of sex, unless we suppose the skulls with the greater development of the single ridge to belong to the female, which is improbable in the highest degree. The skulls with the double and less elevated ridges belong, as proved by No. 1, to the *Simia Wurmbii*; and I am of opinion the single and higher ridge must be referred to another and distinct species, unless we can account for this difference on the score of age. This, I conceive, will be found impossible, as Nos. 7 and 20 are specimens similar to No. 1, with the double and less ele-

vated ridges *decidedly old*, and Nos. 4 and 5 are specimens of the single high ridge, likewise *decidedly old*.

“These three characters in the skulls coincide with the native statements of there being three distinct species in Borneo, and this third Borneon species *may* probably be found to be the *Simia Abelii* or Sumatran Orang. This probability is strengthened by the adult female on her way home : her colour is dark brown, with black face and hands ; and in colour of hair, *contour*, and expression, she differs from the male Orangs, with the callosities, to a degree that makes me doubt her being the female of the same species. I offer you these remarks for fear of accident ; but should the specimens, living and dead, arrive in safety, they will give a fresh impetus to the inquiry, and on my next return to Borneo, I shall, in all probability, be able to set the question at rest, whether there be *two* or *three* species in that country. Believe me, my dear Sir, with best wishes, to remain,

“ Yours very truly,
“ J. BROOKE.”

Mr. Charlesworth exhibited to the Meeting a collection of skins of Mammalia and Birds, which he had obtained on the table-land of Mexico, and which he begged to present to the Society. Among the Mammals were adult specimens of the *Bassaris astuta*, Licht., of which animal a young individual had been procured by Messrs. Thompson and Charlesworth at Real del Monte, and forwarded, under the care of the Society's Corresponding Member, Lieut. Smith, as a present to the Menagerie.

The *Bassaris*, Mr. Charlesworth observed, is known in Mexico by the name ‘Cacomistle’ ; it is abundant in the city itself, and indeed Mr. Charlesworth believes it is not to be met with at a distance from the abodes of man. Its habits are nocturnal, and it selects for its dwelling outhouses or uninhabited buildings, whence it sallies forth at night and commits great ravages in hen-roosts and pigeon-houses, and on this account every attempt is made by the Mexicans to exterminate it. The number of young which the *Bassaris* produces does not exceed three or four at a birth.

A skin of the *Ascomys Mexicanus*, Licht., or ‘Tusa,’ as it is called by the natives, was also exhibited by Mr. Charlesworth ; and he drew attention to a curious fact in the economy of this Rodent, viz. that the cheek-pouches with which it is provided, and which open externally, are used for the purpose of conveying the soil from its subterranean retreats to the surface of the ground, where the mould is deposited in heaps, similar in appearance to those formed by the common Mole.

The skulls of these two animals were on the table ; and Mr. Waterhouse observed, that that of *Bassaris astuta* presented all the characters of the skulls of the *Paradoxuri*, whilst the skull of *Ascomys Mexicanus* did not appear to him to offer any characters by which it might be distinguished (excepting as a *species*) from the crania of different species of *Geomys* which he had examined ; and as the same remarks would apply to the dentition, he thought it would be desirable to expunge one of these genera from our catalogues.

The following paper, entitled "Descriptions of several new species of *Chitones*, brought by H. Cuming, Esq., from the Philippine Islands," by G. B. Sowerby, Esq., jun., was next read.

CHITON SPINIGER. *Ch. Spiniger*, Mag. Nat. Hist. 1840, p. 287; Con. Illus., f. 68. *Ch. testá depressá, ovato-elongatá, omninò granulatá; valvis reclinantibus, terminalibus rotundatis; margine lato, spinis sub-arcuatis numerosis instructo.*

Long. $2\frac{1}{10}$; lat. $1\frac{1}{2}$ poll.

The description is here repeated, for the purpose of noticing two remarkable varieties brought by Mr. Cuming from the Philippines.

In the first variety the spines are comparatively short, and being coated in patches by calcareous matter, give to the margin an appearance of being banded with black and white. The valves are more rounded, and in some instances more coarsely granulated than in the specimens originally described. Found under stones at low water in Cagayan, province of Misamis, island Mindinão.

In the second variety the valves are more elevated. Found under stones at low water, in the island Siquijor.

The larger variety tends to connect the species with the variable *Ch. piceus*, from which it differs in the narrowness of the valves, the spinose margin, and the purplish flesh tint of the inside, which are the same in all the varieties.

CHITON ALATUS. *Ch. testá elongatá, subdepressá, griseo-virescente, fusco-virescente maculatá; valvis anticè coarctatis, primá et ultimá asperis; areis dorsalibus rotundatis, granoso-striatis; margine squamoso-granulato.*

Hab. ad insulam Siquijor et Zebu.

More depressed, having the marginal granulations coarser and the lateral areas more expanded than *Ch. limaciformis*.

Found under stones at low water.

CHITON TRUNCATUS. *Ch. testá ovali, minutissimè asperá, roséd aut pallidè fulvá, griseo-virescente maculatá, sulcis subdistantibus leviter undatá; areis lateralibus elevatis, expansis; valvá posticá conicá, anticè subcomplanatá, posticè truncatá; margine lævi.*

Long. 1.50; lat. .80.

Hab. ad insulam Siquijor, Philippinarum.

Differing from *Ch. crenulatus*, Grayi, &c., chiefly in the conical shape and sudden termination of the last valve. The species is subject to great variations, both in the colour and in the strength of the undulating lines. Found under stones at low water.

Var. *testá sublævi.*

Hab. ad insulam Samar (Catbalonga).

CHITON INCISUS. *Ch. testá elongatá, grised, fusco-maculatá; valvis angustis, subdisjunctis, elongatis, longitudinaliter undato-striatis, primá sexfariam costatá, medianis utrinque unicastis; areis centralibus latis, ultimá subconicá, utrinque trifariam costatá; fissurá triangulari posticè incisá; margine lato, fasciculis minutissimis numerosis instructo, posticè inciso.*

Long. 2.60 ; lat. 1 poll.

Hab. ad insulam Zebu (Daleguete).

It is to be regretted that no specimens of this very remarkable species should have been preserved with the soft parts ; it being probable that the fissure in the last valve and in the posterior part of the margin is accompanied by some anatomical peculiarity in the animal sufficient to establish its claim to generic distinction.

Found under stones at low water.

CHITON COARCTATUS. *Ch. testá elongatá, posticè coarctatá, subtunicatá; valvis reniformibus, subdisjunctis, carinatis, asperis; cariná dorsali lævi; margine lævi.*

Long. 1 ; lat. .50 poll.

Hab. ad insulam Bohol, Philippinarum.

From the peculiar shape of the valves, and the comparative smallness of the portion which remains uncovered, the observer would be led to look for the small tufts of hair found in the margins of some similarly-shaped species. All the specimens, however, have the margins perfectly smooth.

Found under stones at low water.

July 27, 1841.

In consequence of there not being a sufficient number of Members present to constitute a quorum, no Meeting took place.